

and splitting pattern of these signals in the off resonance decoupled spectrum are characteristic of flavan-3-ols¹²; δ 156.47 (s, C-5), 156.20 (s, C-4' and -7), 153.72 (s, C-8a), 129.93 (s, C-1'), 128.19 (d, C-2' and -6'), 114.37 (d, C-3' and -5'), 98.39 (s, C-4a), 95.09 (d, C-6), 94.06 (d, C-8), 78.02 (d, C-2), 64.80 (d, C-3) and 28.30 (t, C-4). This is the first report of ¹³C nmr of (-)epiafzelechin.

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Phytochemical Examination of *Spilanthus acemella* (Murr.)

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IN consideration of various medicinal properties¹ and various reports² on *Spilanthus acemella* Murr. (Fam. : Compositae) we undertook further investigation on the plant. In the present communication we report some of our results.

The air-dried whole plant of *S. acemella* was extracted successively with petroleum ether and

ethanol. The petroleum ether extract on chromatography (silica gel) and elution with petroleum ether-benzene (9 : 1) furnished colourless crystalline needles, m.p. 86°; $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3 425 (OH) and 1 050 cm^{-1} (C—O) which was identified as myricyl alcohol (1), (m.m.p., co-tlc and co-ir). Its acetate melted at 72°. The petroleum ether-benzene (4 : 1) eluent gave colourless shining flakes soluble in NaHCO_3 , m.p. 59°; $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1 730 cm^{-1} (acid C=O) which was identified as palmitic acid (2) by usual comparison (m.m.p., co-tlc, co-ir). Elution of the column with petroleum ether-benzene (2 : 1) gave white flakes, soluble in NaHCO_3 , m.p. 69°; $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1 730 cm^{-1} (acid C=O) and which was identified as stearic acid (3) from its ¹H nmr spectrum and usual comparison (m.m.p., co-tlc, co-ir). The petroleum ether-benzene (1 : 1) eluent gave a solid, m.p. 223–25°; $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1 732 cm^{-1} (ester C=O), positive to Salkowski's reaction for triterpenoids. Hydrolysis of the compound gave a solid, m.p. 181–83°, identical with α -amyrin. So the compound was identified as α -amyrin acetate (4).

The petroleum ether-benzene (1 : 2) eluent gave β -sitosterol (5) m.p. 137°, identified from its ¹H nmr and mass spectra and by usual comparison (m.m.p., co-tlc and co-ir). The benzene eluent gave a solid, m.p. 148–50°, which was identified as β -amyrin (6) which was identified from its ¹H nmr spectra and its acetate and also by usual comparison (m.m.p., co-tlc, co-ir).

Elution of column with benzene-ethyl acetate (9 : 1) gave a solid, m.p. 182°, which was found to be identical to the hydrolysis product of 4, and was identified as α -amyrin (7).

The concentrated ethanol extract was extracted with ether. The residue obtained on evaporation of ether was repeatedly crystallised with CHCl_3 - $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}$ (1 : 1) to white crystals, m.p. 302–03°d, $[\alpha]_D - 38^\circ$ (pyridine), positive to Molisch's test for sugars. It was found to be a phytosterolin and the mass spectrum of the compound indicated it to be a mixture of β -sitosterol-D(+)-glucoside and stigmastérol-D(+)-glucoside.

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NOTES

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Phytochemical Examination of *Cressa cretica* Linn. (Rudanti)

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IN view of the medicinal importance¹ of *Cressa cretica* Linn. (Fam.: Convulvulaceae), we undertook a systematic chemical investigation of the plant.

The air-dried, powdered whole plant of *C. cretica* was extracted successively with petroleum ether, acetone, ethyl acetate and ethanol. From the petroleum ether extract after chromatographed over silica gel and elution with petroleum ether a crystalline compound, m.p. 82°; $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3 450 (OH), 715 and 725 cm^{-1} (n-alkyl chain)² was isolated and identified as n-octacosanol (1) by the usual comparison (m.m.p., co-tlc, co-ir). From the chloroform-benzene (1:1) eluent of the chromatogram β -sitosterol (2), m.p. 137° was isolated (identified from its m.m.p., ¹H nmr).

The acetone extract after chromatography and elution with benzene-ethyl acetate (9:1) gave colourless needles, m.p. 202°, which was identified as scopoletin (3) from its ir, uv and ¹H nmr spectra. From the benzene-ethyl acetate (4:1) eluent a crystalline solid, m.p. 231–32°, was isolated and identified as umbelliferone (4) from its ir, uv and ¹H nmr spectra and usual comparison (m.m.p., co-tlc and co-ir). The ethyl acetate-chloroform (1:1) eluent gave yellow needles, m.p. 150°, which was identified as isopimpinellin (5) from its uv, ir, ¹H nmr and mass spectra.

The concentrated ethyl acetate extract of the plant on cooling gave a crystalline compound, m.p. 290°, which on acid hydrolysis gave β -sitosterol and D(+)-glucose, identified by paper chromatography. Identity of the compound as β -sitosterol-D(+)-glucoside (6) was confirmed from its ¹H nmr and mass spectra.

The concentrated ethanol extract after chromatography (silica gel) and elution with ethyl acetate

gave a yellow solid, m.p. 312.15°; $\lambda_{\max}$ (MeOH) 370 nm, which was identified as quercetin (7) from its colour reactions, uv data (m.m.p., co-tlc and co-ir).

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Isorhamnetin 3-O-Rutinoside from *Syzygium cumini* Linn.

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THE plant *Syzygium cumini* Linn. (commonly known as *Jamun* in Hindi) is used as medicine for several diseases¹. Several common flavonoids², kaempferol, quercetin, myricetin, isoquercetin and isoprenoids³, oleanolic acid and betulinic acid have been reported by various workers. The present work was undertaken to reveal the presence of other biodynamic constituents.

Experimental

The roots of the plant were collected from village Khaira (District Bilaspur) in the month of October 1988 and were authenticated⁴. The shade-dried crude material (80 kg) was extracted by boiling ethanol and the *in vacuo* concentrated extract was partitioned between water and different organic solvents (from non-polar to polar). The ethyl acetate extract after repeated column chromatography over silica gel gave a compound which was homogeneous to tlc, hRf 20 (30% AcOH), 60 (BAW) on cellulose plates, m.p. 182°, and was found to be a flavonoid glycoside by usual tests⁵; $\lambda_{\max}$ (MeOH) 253, 267sh, 355; (+NaOMe) 270, 299sh, 409; (+AlCl₃) 270, 299sh, 407; (+AlCl₃/

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